

Taxonomic notes on longhorned beetles with the descriptions of several new taxa (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, new genus, new subgenus, new synonyms, new rank, another subfamily added.

Abstract: Many newly published taxonomy modifications are discussed. Several taxonomy news is proposed.

Introduction.

Many taxonomic publications on Cerambycidae are regularly appear each year without special comments by colleagues. I propose here alternative positions on several questionable cases. Several new synonyms cannot be accepted. Several new names were in fact synonyms. Certain taxonomy acts were not acceptable. Rank of six species names was downgraded to subspecies. A new genus and a new subgenus were proposed, as well as many new synonyms. One old subfamily name was restored, as well as one subspecies name. A wrong geographical record was corrected, as well as some other wrongly published data. Rank of one old name was restored.

1. A new unacceptable tribal system of Lepturinae was proposed by Zamoroka (2022b): Cariliini (*Carilia*, *Acmaeops*, *Gaurotus*, *Paragaurotus*, *Dinoptera*, *Gnathacmaeops*, *Cortodera*); Pidoniini (Pidonia, Fallacea), Evodiini (Evodinus, Brachyta). Lepturini includes 6 Palaearctic genera (Anoplodera, Nivellia, Leptura, Anastrangalia, Grammoptera, Strangalia); Stenocorini - 2 (Stenocorus, Anisorus), Rhamnusiini - 3 (Rhamnusium, Akimerus, Enoploderes), Rhagiini - 2 (Pachyta, Rhagium).

Cortodera cannot be in one tribe with all genera around *Dinoptera*; *Rhamnusium*, *Akimerus*, and *Enoploderes* are totally

M.A. Lazarev

different on larval and imaginal characters, so until better decisions it is necessary conserve traditional system of Palaearctic Lepturinae with 7 tribes: Xylosteini, Encyclopini, Oxymirini, Enoploderini, Rhamnusiini, Rhagiini, Lepturini.

2. *Evodinellus borealis* (Gyllenhal, 1827) = *Pidonia petrovi* Danilevsky, 2023a, **syn. nov.** on the base of the type series study.

3. *Megarhagium* Reitter, 1913 and *Hagrium* Villiers, 1978 must be accepted as valid genera names as in Villier (1978).

4. Very different genera *Brachysomida* Casey, 1913 and *Pseudogaurotina* Plavilstshikov, 1958 were inadequately published by Zamoroka (2022b) as subgenera of one genus, and impossible combination was proposed: “*Brachysomida (Pseudogaurotina) excellens*”.

5. According to Zamoroka (2022b), “*Evodinus borealis* does not belong to the separate genus *Evodinellus* Winkler, 1929” or *Evodinus* LeConte, 1850 = *Evodinellus* Plavilstshikov, 1915. But American *Evodinus* differs from *Evodinellus borealis* (Gyllenhal, 1827) by the position of antennal insertions, which are situated in *Evodinellus borealis* in front of anterior eye margins, while in *Evodinus* antennal insertions disposed behind the line connecting anterior eye margins.

6. The names of very different genera: *Acmaeops* LeConte, 1850 and *Euracmaeops* Danilevsky, 2014 were wrongly published by Zamoroka (2022b) as synonyms.

7. Wrong synonyms were accepted by Zamoroka (2022a):

“*Cortodera flavimana* (Waltl, 1838) = *C. moldovana* Danilevsky, 1995”. In fact, *C. moldovana* has no connection with *C. flavimana*, but close to *C. tibialis* (Marseul, 1876), and especially to *C. tibialis rossica* Danilevsky, 2001b. No evidences of the presence of *C. flavimana* and *C. moldovana* in Ukraine exist.

M.A. Lazarev

8. *Cornumutilla quadrivittata* (Gebler, 1830) was wrongly recorded for Ukraine by Zamoroka (2018, 2022a). *C. quadrivittata* is widely distributed in Siberia (Lazarev, 2009) and does not penetrate to Europe. A single record for Moscow Region was very doubtful. Only *C. lineata* (Letzner, 1844) is distributed in Europe.

9. *Pedostrangalia revestita corsica* Vartanis, 2024b, **stat. nov.** was described from France (Corsica) as a species on the bases of red anterior legs in combination with black other legs. No other features are observed that distinguish the new taxon from *P. r. revestita*.

10. The reality of two different subgenera of *Stictoleptura* [*Paracorymbia* sensu Miroshnikov, 2021, 2016] subgen. *Batesiata* Miroshnikov, 1998 and *S.* subgen. *Pyrrholeptura* Lazarev, 2016 was not accepted by Miroshnikov (2016, 2021). I insist on three fundamental differences: *Pyrrholeptura* is characterized by red elytral color, shallow male abdominal emargination and dense elytral punctation. The difference in color between two subgenera can't be denied, but Miroshnikov shows several examples of different taxa where elytral color is not important. Such reasoning is irrelevant. He shows male abdominal emargination in both species, but the shape of those structures in his photos is distinctly different, as well as elytral punctation in his photos of “*P. (Batesiata) tesserula*” and “*P. (B.) pyrrha*”. So, *Stictoleptura (Batesiata)* Miroshnikov, 1998 and *S. (Pyrrholeptura)* Lazarev, 2016 are good valid names.

11. *Stictoleptura (Maculileptura)* Danilevsky, 2014) was not accepted by Miroshnikov (2021) who did not see the differences of this taxon from *Paracorymbia* (s. str.) Miroshnikov, 1998. But that valid name was established by Danilevsky (2014) instead of *Paracorymbia* (s. str.) «group *maculicornis*» Miroshnikov (1998). All characters of the group were published by Miroshnikov (1998: 594): Last abdominal male sternite with shallow, narrow, short, but well distinct impression, slightly emarginated apically; hind male tibiae not curved, with two apical spines; elytra yellowish, monochrome or with dark apex and lateral margin; antennal joints with light bases or with light rings.

M.A. Lazarev

12. Several new synonyms are proposed: *Xylotrechus* (*Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860 = *Fulvotrechus* Zamoroka, 2021 = *Hieroglyphotrechus* Zamoroka, 2021 = *Ignetrechus* Zamoroka, 2021 = **syn. nn.**), *Xylotrechus* Chevrolat, 1860 = *Spinotrechus* Zamoroka, 2021, **syn. nov.**

In general Zamoroka's publications were often based on molecular data, but strong morphological argument were usually ignored. For example, such cases as one tribe for so different genera as *Rhamnusia*, *Akimerus* and *Enoploderes*, as well as joining of *Rutpela maculata* (Poda von Neuhaus, 1761) and *Stenurella nigra* (Linnaeus, 1758) inside one genus show complete absurdity of his method.

13. Wrong synonyms proposed by Zamoroka (2021): *Xylotrechus* = *Rusticoclytus* must be rejected, and valid name *Xylotrechus* (*Rusticoclytus* Vives, 1977) generally accepted (Vives, 1977, 2000; Villiers, 1978, 1979; Demelt, 1982; Bílý & Mehl, 1989; Marquet, 2001, 2015; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007; Sama, 2008; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2012, 2020; Alekseev & Maryutin, 2019; Stolbov et al., 2019; Trócoli, 2019; Gradinarov & Sivilov, 2020; Sakalian et al., 2020 and others) must be preserved.

14. *Xyloclytus* was wrongly upgraded to genus rank by Zamoroka (2021). Valid subgenus name *Xylotrechus* (*Xyloclytus* Reitter, 1913) must be preserved.

15. *Teratoclytus* D.W. Zaitzev, 1937 cannot be moved to Anaglyptini, as it was proposed by Zamoroka (2021) and must be returned to Clytini (elytral bases without tubercles).

16. *Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 537 (type species *Cerambyx figuratus* Scopoli, 1763) was introduced as a subgenus of *Chlorophorus*. It was upgraded to genus level by Zamoroka (2021) without sufficient reasons. *Sparganophorus* Zamoroka, 2021 (type species *Clytus diadema* Motschulsky, 1854) was described for a single species, which was placed by Özdikmen (2022) in *Ch. (Humeromaculatus)*, so *Ch. (Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011 = *Sparganophorus* Zamoroka, 2021, **syn. nov.**

M.A. Lazarev

17. *Perderomaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011: 537 (type species *Cerambyx sartor* Müller, 1766) was upgraded by Zamoroka (2021) to genus level without sufficient reasons, the valid name must be *Chlorophorus* (*Perderomaculatus*).

18. *Chlorophorus* (*Viridiphorus* Zamoroka, 2021, type species: *Callidium herbstii* Brahm, 1790) = *Chlorophorus* (*Brevenotatus* Özdikmen, 2022, type species: *Clytus distinguendus* Perroud, 1855), **syn. nov.** as *Ch. herbstii* was included in *Ch. (Brevenotatus)*.

19. New synonyms must be accepted:

Stenurella (*Priscostenurella* Özdikmen, 2013) = *Rutpela* (*Eduardvivesia* Zamoroka, Trócoli, Shparyk & Semaniuk, 2022) = *Rutpela* (*Nigromacularia* Zamoroka, Trócoli, Shparyk & Semaniuk, 2022), **syn. nn.**

20. *Ropalopus hungaricus olympicus* Vartanis, 2024c was described as *R. insubricus olympicus* Vartanis, 2024c from Greece (Olympos Mt., Pieria prov., 700-1000 m), and *R. hungaricus creticus* Vartanis, 2024c was described as a species from Crete.

21. *Chlorophorus* cannot be separated from Clytini, so Clytini Mulsant, 1839 = Chlorophorini Zamoroka, 2021, **syn. nov.**

22. Three new combinations were incorrectly accepted by Zamoroka et. al. (2022): *Rutpela* (*Eduardvivesia*) *vaucheri* (Bedel, 1900), *R. (Nigrostenurella) nigra* (Linnaeus, 1758), *R. (Nigromacularia) septempunctata* (Fabricius 1793). All three taxa must be left in *Stenurella* as: *S. (Priscostenurella) vaucheri*, *S. (P.) septempunctata* and *S. (Nigrostenurella) nigra*.

Several species were placed by Zamoroka et. al. (2022) in wrong subgenera: *Stenurella* (*Priscostenurella*) *jaegeri* (Hummel, 1825), *S. (P.) novercalis* (Reitter, 1901), *S. (s. str.) hybridula* (Reitter, 1902), *S. (s. str.) approximans* (Rosenhauer, 1856). Must be: *S. (Stenurelloides) jaegeri*, *S. (S.) novercalis*, *S. (Iberostenurella) hybridula*, *S. (Crassostenurella) approximans*.

M.A. Lazarev

23. *Oxypleurus nodieri* Mulsant, 1839 was placed by Zamoroka (2022a) in Atimiini without sufficient reasons. The species belongs to Saphanini as it is generally accepted.

24. Wrong synonyms were accepted by Zamoroka (2022a):

“*Tetropium fuscum* (Fabricius, 1787) = *T. tauricum* Shapovalov, 2007”. The holotype of *T. tauricum* strongly differs from many hundreds of known *T. fuscum*. Up to now only very peculiar holotype of *T. tauricum* is known. So, rather probably it was just a teratic specimen of local species - *T. castaneum* (Linnaeus, 1758). According to Plavilstshikov (1940), *T. fuscum* was not collected in Crimea. *T. castaneum* only was recorded for Crimean fauna by Zagaikevich (1991: 153). In fact *T. fuscum* is absent in Crimea. It was only recorded by Bartenev (2009) with question mark on the base of WEB European Cerambycidae list of 2000 by M.L. Danilevsky.

25. *Anoplistes balcanicus* Sláma, 2010 described from Bulgaria was wrongly published as a subspecies of *A. halodendri* (Pallas, 1773) by Danilevsky (2020) on the bases of the records by Muraj (1960) of *Purpuricenus ephippium* for Albania. *Asias ephippium* was also recorded for Bulgaria by Angelov (1995) and for Rumania by Panin, Săvulescu (1961). But in fact, *Anoplistes balcanicus* Sláma, 2010 does not similar to *A. halodendri* because of short antenna and legs, peculiar elytral design. So, *Anoplistes balcanicus* Sláma, 2010 must be accepted as a valid species name, as it was originally introduced. The presence of *Anoplistes halodendri* in Balcan area rests rather doubtful.

26. *Plagionotus detritus caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940 = *P. d. grecus* Vartanis, 2023, **syn. nov.**

Plagionotus detritus caucasicola Plavilstshikov, 1940 was described with two taxonomy rank in the original publication: as “m.” [morpha] and as “форма” [forma]. The later makes the name available, and it was generally accepted (Özdikmen & Turgut, 2009; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2010; Özdikmen, 2014; Vitali, 2016; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2018; Lazarev, 2019; Danilevsky, 2020; Vartanis, 2023 and others).

M.A. Lazarev

Vartanis (2023) accepted *P. d. caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940 as a valid name, but proposed no distinguishing characters. In fact, the Caucasian populations are just identic to Greece populations. Populations from Peloponnesus were described by Vartanis (2023) and I've got good series from Northern Greece (Thessaly): 7 males, 8 females from Ossa Mt. and 1 male, 2 females from near Kalabaka (Meteyora). Greece specimens are also rather pale as specimens from Caucasian populations, have same wide yellow pronotum anteriorly, wide yellow elytral stripes, and posterior elytral stripes are partly or totally conjugated.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow)

SM - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of the Moscow State University

***Plagionotus detritus caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940**

Figs. 1-3

Type locality. Russia, Republic of Adygea, Maykop environs (on the bases of lectotype designation).

Description. Dark areas of pronotum and elytra rather light-brown; elytra with widened transverse yellow stripes behind middle, dark stripes in between very narrow; anterior pronotal yellow area very wide, often joined with central transverse pronotal stripe; narrow yellow transverse stripe behind elytral bases more or less reduced or totally absent; body length: 14.3-17.5 mm.

P. d. detritus (Linnaeus, 1758) is characterized by dark-brown ground color of elytra and pronotum; light central pronotal stripe usually well developed; yellow elytral stripes usually very narrow; body length: 10-19 mm (Plavilstshikov, 1940).

Material. Lectotype (Figs 1-2) designated by Danilevsky (2009), published by Lazarev (2019), male (length: 14.0 mm; width: 4.2 mm) with 4 labels: 1) "Cauc. occ. bor. / Maikop / 25.V.[1]928"; 2) "ex coll. Shaposhnikov"; 3) [red] "LECTOTYPUS / *Plagionotus detritus* / forma CAUCASICOLA / Plavilstshikov, 1940 / M. Danilevsky des., 2008"; 4) [pink] "Зоомузей МГУ (Москва,

M.A. Lazarev

РОССИЯ) / № ZMMU Col 00180 / Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ. / (Mosquae, ROSSIA) / ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov” - ZMM; Paralectotype (Fig. 3): 1 female, Maykop, 5.6.1935 - ZMM.

Additional materials. 1 male, Krasnodar Reg., L’vovskaya, 16.6.1966 - ZMM; 1 female, Ekaterinodar, 9.7.1914, Lyutkovsky - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Stavropol, V. Lutshnik - ZMM; 1 male, Armenia, Dilizhan, 5000’, 26.7.1934, N. Plavilstshikov - ZMM; 1 female, Transcauc., Kars - ZMM; 1 male, Krasnodar, Novopokhladnoe, 13.6.1956-1959 - MD; 1 female, Sochi, Lazarevskoe, 4.8.1983, A. Koval - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, Ubinskoe, 10.5.1976, M. Kravchenko - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, Ubinskoe, 2.5.1991, A. Abramov - MD; 1 male, Krasnodar, Ubinskoe, 5.8.1976, Belov - ML; 1 male, Krasnodar, Novopokhladnoe, 25.5.1959 - MD;. 3 males (Fig. 4), 4 females (Fig. 5), Ossa Mt. (East), VII.2001, P. Tauzin - ML; 4 males, 4 females, with the same label - SM; 1 male, 2 females, 1-2 km N Kalabaka, Meteora, VI, 1981, M. Sláma - ML.

Distribution. Russia, North Caucasus, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Turkey; Greece (Thessaly, Peloponnesus); the records for Syria (Plavilstshikov, 1940; Danilevsky, 2020; Vartanis, 2023) were most probably connected with *P. detritus africaeseptentrionalis* Tippmann, 1952.

27. *Dorcadion fulvum erythropterum* Fischer von Waldheim, 1823 = *Dorcadion fulvum opillicum* Zamoroka, 2019, **syn. nov.** Big available series of the species (including series from “Opillya” - geographic region of the Podolian Upland in Lvov Oblast, Ivano-Frankovsk Oblast and Ternopol Oblast in western Ukraine) show a great degree of geographical variability masking local forms.

28. *Dorcadion fulvum heracles* Vartanis, 2024a, **stat. nov.** was described from Greece (Olympus Mt., Pieria prov.) as a species on the bases of black first antennal joint and black anterior legs. No other features are observed that distinguish the new taxon from *D. f. fulvum* (Scopoli, 1763).

M.A. Lazarev

29. The new wrong synonyms were published by Zamoroka (2022a): without analyses of corresponding materials and with false statement: “ranges of some of them completely overlap”. “*Dorcadion cinerarium cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) = *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932 = *D. c. zubovi* Lazarev, 2011”, “*D. c. panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951 = *D. c. bartenevi* Lazarev, 2011 = *D. c. skrylniki* Lazarev, 2011 = *D. c. azovense* Lazarev, 2011 = *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996 = *D. c. demidovi* Danilevsky, 2013 = *D. c. mosyakini* Danilevsky, 2021”; “*Dorcadion equestre* (Laxmann, 1770) = *D. e. vadimi* Danilevsky, 2021”; “*Dorcadion holosericeum* Krynicki, 1832 = *D. h. ustynovi* Danilevsky, 2021”. Most probably Zamoroka did not know such specimens, so, valid names must be preserved: *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932; *D. c. zubovi* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. bartenevi* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. skrylniki* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. azovense* Lazarev, 2011; *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996; *D. c. demidovi* Danilevsky, 2013; *D. c. mosyakini* Danilevsky, 2021; *D. e. vadimi* Danilevsky, 2021; *D. h. ustynovi* Danilevsky, 2021.

30. The wrong synonyms *Falsomesosella truncatipennis* Pic, 1944 = *F. taibaishana* Lazarev, 2021 published by Lin, Weigel & Ge (2021), can't be accepted, as holotype of *F. truncatipennis* (depicted by Lin et al., 2021) from Zhejiang (see Lin, 2015) is distinctly wider with more elongated prothorax, besides its type area is strongly distant. So, *F. taibaishana* Lazarev, 2021 is a valid name.

31. *Quasimesosella ussuriensis* was recorded by Danilevsky (2023b: 334) for the south of Khabarovsk Region (Listvyanaya River), but according to personal communication by N. Anisimov (November, 2023), that record must be connected with Listvenichnaya River from Malyi Khingan in Jewish Autonomous Republic. The record of that species for Duchin must be connected with Dichun River south-eastwards Radde (Jewish Autonomous Republic).

32. *Paratetrops* **gen. nov.**

Type species. *Tetrops warncke* Holzschuh, 1977.

Description. Body densely covered with long thick black erect setae; antennae extremely sick, with apical joints about as long as wide;

M.A. Lazarev

pronotum with smooth central stripe; elytra with rough big punctation. A single species distributed in south Turkey is known - *Paratetrops warnckei* (Holzschuh, 1977), **new rank**.

Etymology. close to *Tetrops*. Gender masculine.

33. *Tetrops peterkai* Scořepa, 2020 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Tetrops praeustus peterkai* Scořepa, 2020, **stat. nov.**; type locality: Czech Republic, Moravia, Horní Pole environs.

According to the original description the species is distributed in Czech Republic, Slovakia, Austria, Germany.

34. *Tetrops praetermitus* Sláma, 2020a is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Tetrops praeustus praetermitus* Sláma, 2020, **stat. nov.**; type locality. Bohemia, Lásenice. According to Sláma (2020b) the taxon is distributed in South Bohemia only.

35. *Phytoecia (Musaria) rubropunctata* (Goeze 1777) was wrongly recorded for Ukraine by Zamoroka (2022a). It is a West European species absent in Ukraine; it does not penetrate east of Germany (Bense, 1995; Sama, 2003), but was recently recorded for Spain, France and Italy only (Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020). Old wrong published records could be based on specimens of *Ph. (M.) argus* (Frölich, 1793) or *Ph. (M.) faldermanni* (Faldermann, 1837).

36. A new subgenus *Phytoecia (Danilevskia)* **subgen. nov.**, type species: *Saperda molybdaena* Dalman, 1817) is proposed for 4 species: *Ph. (Danilevskia) molybdaena* (Dalman, 1817), *Ph. (Danilevskia) uncinata* (W. Redtenbacher, 1842), *Ph. (Danilevskia) tenuilinea* Fairmaire, 1876 and *Ph. (Danilevskia) badenkoi* Danilevsky, 1988. The new taxon is characterized by the absence of the dense solid elytral scaly cover consisting of small scales or very short setae. Such cover is typical for *Ph. (Opsilia)* Mulsant, 1862). Besides all *Ph. (Danilevskia)* has unicuspid mandibulae and eyes with joined dorsal and ventral lobes. New subgenus name is feminine. The name is dedicated to Mikhail Leontievich Danilevsky - a specialist on Palaearctic Cerambycidae and my constant colleague.

M.A. Lazarev

37. Up to now Palaearctic Cerambycidae includes 8 subfamilies (Parandrinae, Prioninae, Lepturinae, Necydalinae, Spondylidinae, Apatophyseinae, Cerambycinae, Lamiinae). Now another one must be accepted: Agapanthiinae Mulsant, 1839 (type genus *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835, monobasic), which was traditionally included in Lamiinae.

Agapanthiinae is characterized by moderately or small body size; usually strongly elongated; parallel sided or with sides slightly diverging posteriorly; antennae usually long, often much longer than body, usually 12-segmented (in *Pseudocalamobius* - 11-segmented); frons usually sloping backwards; prothorax always without lateral spines or tubercles; legs short; anterior coxae spherical; claws simple, divergent, without tooth-like appendages or denticles; metepisternae very narrow, parallel sided. Larvae with cylindrical "C"-like curved body, without legs; head slightly elongated, strongly prominent; abdominal ventral ampullae partly reduced.

Agapanthiinae differ from Lamiinae by many larval characters: "C"-like curved body, slightly elongated head, rounded laterally, ventral ampullae partly or totally reduced.

38. *Agapanthia kindermanni* Pic, 1905 must be returned to the original subspecies rank as *Agapanthia dahli kindermanni* Pic, 1905.

39. *Agapanthia lateralis* Ganglbauer, 1884 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli lateralis* Ganglbauer, 1884, **stat. nov.**

40. *Agapanthia mutinensium* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli mutinensium* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010, **stat. nov.**

41. *Agapanthia pustulifera* Pic, 1905 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli pustulifera* Pic, 1905, **stat. nov.**

42. *Agapanthia salviae* Holzschuh, 1975 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli salviae* Holzschuh, 1975, **stat. nov.**

M.A. Lazarev

43. *Agapanthia schurmanni* Sama, 1979 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli schurmanni* Sama, 1979, **stat. nov.**

44. *Agapanthia subsimplicicornis* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Agapanthia dahli subsimplicicornis* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2010, **stat. nov.**

45. Zaitzev D.W. (original spelling - Zaitzev 1931, 1937) was wrongly published several times (Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020) as Zaitzev D.A. The original spelling was unacceptably changed by Zamoroka (2021) to “Zajciw”.

Acknowledgements. I am very grateful to M. Danilevsky (A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia), A. Gusakov (Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia) and S. Murzin (Moscow, Russia) for supplying me with material for study. My special thanks to M. Danilevsky for permanent consultations.

Figs 1-5. *Plagionotus detritus caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1940:
1. Lectotype, male; 2. Lectotype labels; 3. Paralectotype, female, Maykop,
5.6.1935; 4. Male, Ossa Mt. (East), VII.2001, P. Tausin;
5. Female with the same label.

M.A. Lazarev

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Received: 20.12.2023

Accepted: 29.01.2024